

HADITH AS A TOOL OF EDUCATION AND UPBRINGING

Bayan Qambarova

Teacher of the high-class primary school of the 31st general
secondary school in Yangiyul district, Tashkent region

abduvaxonovamuxlisa18@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10005715>

Annotation

The article highlights the important aspects of the use of hadiths in the formation of the spiritual qualities of primary school students. Their role in human development is based. The content of the methods that can be used within the framework of the age characteristics of the students is discussed.

Key words: hadith, muhaddis, prophet, education, proverb, wisdom, manners.

Our holy sources, which are of great educational importance in the moral and aesthetic education of students - the Holy Qur'an, examples of Hadith, fairy tales, epics, stories, narrations, parables, proverbs, wise words, Imam al-Bukhari, at- Hadiths of Termizi, Yusuf Khos Khajib's "Qutadgu Bilig", Kaikovus's "Nightmare", Alisher Navoi's "Hayrat ul-Abror", "Mahbub ul-Qulub", "Javahirnama" by Husayn Vaiz Koshifi, "Turkish Gulistan or Ethics" by Abdulla Awlani. and works of modern children's poets and writers can be used.

Planning elementary school reading or education lessons based on the principle of simple to complex, taking into account the age characteristics, needs, interests, inclinations and knowledge levels of students, provides certain efficiency. It is important to choose educational methods based on the genre and theme of each work. For example, in education lessons, along with topics such as the activities of great scholars of the East, exemplary thoughts, childhood and old age, thrift, hard work, moderation and caution, sense of country, attitude to nature, wisdom in narrations, hadiths, proverbs, and wise words are taught to students. is a solid foundation for the formation of spirituality.

In order to cover the subject of hadiths, the teacher must thoroughly prepare for the lesson, get to know their ideas, the lives and activities of great muhaddiths. Books of Imam al-Bukhari and al-Tirmizi, images of al-Bukhari's memorial complexes in Samarkand and al-Tirmiziys memorial complexes in Termiz can be used as visual aids. Pupils learn examples of hadiths about manners in the "Reading" and "Education" classes in primary education. Therefore, it is appropriate to start the lesson by asking the following questions that encourage students to think.

1. What hadiths have you memorized? 2. What human qualities are promoted in hadiths? 3. What bad habits are condemned? 4. Have you observed the influence of hadiths on the behavior of yourself or your peers? After getting answers to these questions, information about hadiths will be given.

Hadith is the second holy source after the Qur'an. Hadiths reflect the life and habits, religious and moral skills of our Prophet Muhammad. At this point, it is permissible to comment on the meaning of the word "Prophet" to the students. It is explained that Prophet is a Persian word, "prophet" means "message", "bar" means conveying the word of God to people [4; p. 205]. Hadiths are a rich spiritual and educational treasure that brings a person to perfection and encourages him to good and meritorious deeds. Human virtues such as brotherhood, kinship, rights of parents and children, kindness, honesty, purity, justice, honesty are promoted in hadiths. At the same time, vices such as lying, arrogance, enmity, and oppression are condemned. In particular, the life and hadiths of Prophet Muhammad are an example for people. Scholars engaged in the science of hadith are known as Muhaddis. Al-Bukhari and al-Tirmiziy are scholars who made a great contribution to the development of hadith science.

The First President of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov evaluates these two great figures and their activities in the book "High Spirituality - Invincible Power" as follows: "About the unique contribution of our great thinker and scholars to the development of Islamic culture. First of all, we respectfully mention the blessed names of our grandfather, Imam Bukhari, who has rightfully gained great fame in the Muslim world as the "Sultan of Muhaddiths". This is the most reliable collection of hadiths, which is the culmination of the legacy of this respected Prophet - the book "Al-jame' as-sahih" is the second holy source in the Islamic religion after the Holy Qur'an, and according to the belief of the people of Islam, it is considered the greatest of books written by mankind. For twelve centuries, this book has been illuminating the hearts of millions of people with the light of faith, inviting them to the path of truth and religion [1; p. 38].

The spiritual heritage of our great compatriot - Abu Isa Muhammad ibn Isa Termizi, including the work "Sunani Termizi", is highly valued in the Muslim world. Alloma's ideas promoting fairness, justice, and humanity, which have been a program for scientists and scholars for centuries, are noteworthy for their importance in solving many moral and spiritual issues of our present complex era" [1; p. 39]. After that, hadiths about pleasing parents, honest work, getting knowledge, being kind to people, generosity, being moral, the vice of

stinginess, politeness, greeting are read together with the students, the content is analyzed is made and summarized.

The degree to which the students have mastered the meaning of hadiths can be determined by dividing them into small groups and assigning them tasks. For example: a picture of a big tree is drawn on paper. It is called "Had i s l a r" tree. Various fruits are prepared and hung on the branches of the tree. Boxes are placed behind the "fruits" to ask questions. The leader of the group or one of the members takes the questions from the fruit they like from the tree. Group members prepare together to answer. Questions based on students' life experiences and observations can be as follows:

1. What should children do to get their parents' approval?
2. When and what did you do to please your parents? Why were they happy for you?
3. Have you tried to talk your friend out of it when you saw them lying?
4. What do you do when you see your classmates misbehaving with each other?
5. Can you be kind to others even when you are in a bad mood?
6. Do you take it well when others tell you that you are doing something wrong?
7. Can you control yourself when you are angry?
8. Have you wasted your time and regretted it later?

Answers are asked from the students on the basis of explaining the events and situations they have seen, known, and participated in. In studying the hadiths of Imam al-Bukhari and at-Tirmidhi, students are divided into 2 groups, and each group is assigned the task of filling in the empty cells on the posters with the following figures. One group fills in the boxes of "good qualities" and the other "bad habits". It is also appropriate to use the test method to strengthen students' knowledge. Pre-prepared test questions and answer sheets will be distributed to the students.

1. Find the answer with the names of the great inventors.

A. Navoi, Babur.

V. Al-Bukhari, at-Tirmidhi.

S. Ibn Sina, Beruni.

2. What human qualities are glorified in hadiths?

A. Kindness, purity, honesty.

V. Honesty, justice, generosity.

Q. Answers A and B are correct

3. There are two things that most people do not appreciate. One is health, the other is ...

A. Free time

V. Honesty

S. Justice

4. It is charity to show the right path to those who have gone astray. What is this?

A. Wisdom

V. Hadith

S. Poem

5. What is the greatest sin?

A. Biting

V. Lying

S. Swearing at parents

Answers are collected. Pupils and groups who actively participate in the lesson are encouraged. Memorizing hadiths is given as homework. In conclusion, the teaching of hadiths from the elementary grades is a factor in raising the young generation to be intellectually and spiritually perfect

References:

1. Karimov I.A. Yuksak ma'naviyat – yengilmas kuch. – Toshkent: Ma'naviyat, 2008. – 173 b.

2. Husanboeva Q. Tahlil – adabiyotni anglash yo'li. – Toshkent: Muharrir, 2013. – 432 b.

3. Kambarova S. Hadislarda ezgulik talqini // Boshlang'ich ta'lim. – Toshkent, 2008. № 12. – B. 14–15.

4. O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. P harfi. – Toshkent: "O'zbekiston Milliy ensiklopediyasi" Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti. www.ziyouz.com kutbxonasi.

5. Mamiraliyev Q.Q. O'zbek she'riyatida shakliy izlanishlar va individuallik.// O'zbekistonda xorijiy tillar. — 2022. — № 5 (46). — B. 201-218.

<https://doi.org/10.36078/1673348607>

